

THE REASONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONGENITAL CYSTS OF THE NECK AND IMPROVING THE PREVENTION OF THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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The congenital cyst and leakage pathways of the neck are relatively rare within embryonic developmental defects. Gubaydulina E.Ya. and Tsegolnik L.N. according to the data of tumors and tumors found in the face-jaw and neck, their proportion is barely 5% within the normal derivatives, while patients in this pathology make up 2% of all patients in the facial-jaw division.

Goal. The reasons for the development of the congenital cyst and outflow tract of the neck consist in deep study and improvement of methods of treatment.

The onset of congenital cysts and leakage pathways of the neck corresponds to the first weeks of embryonic development, the manifestation of clinical signs of the disease can occur at different age periods – from new birth to old age.

Currently, at 6.5 weeks of age, the jabra cracks of the embryo have been proven to bring their dressing (the first swallow pocket – in the Eustachian niche, the second – in the almond – shaped bay, the third-in the bovine and parathyroid glands, pear-shaped pockets of the pharynx). The lateral area of the neck is located between the inner outer sleeping artery, similar to the second swallowing pocket, and the palate opens into the inner oral sac in the tonsils. The topographic features of the lateral axes of the neck, as in the case from birth, make it possible to distinguish them as anamalia in the development of a second reticulated fissure involving the second pharyngeal sac and cervical sinus. The lateral cysts are located directly on the neurovascular bundle of the neck at the level of bifurcation of the common sleeping artery.

Mass prophylaxis is achieved in general, first of all, by eliminating the causes and conditions of the development of the disease, as well as increasing the resistance of the parental body. However, it should be noted that all these research methods do not allow the huckm of histogenesis of coistal formations, which often leads to errors in their diagnosis. For this reason, the establishment of the final diagnosis remains in the sphere of morphological activity, which can determine the histogenetic dependence of the pathological process on Khol, which uses histological and cytological methods.

Conclusion. Summing up, it can be said that the success in the treatment of congenital cysts and leakage pathways of the neck depends on the degree of knowledge of embryology and their timely detection in the field using modern diagnostic methods.

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